

SAVING LIVES THROUGH TECHNOVATIVE FLATPACK EMERGENCY SHELTERS USING BAMBOO-CORRUGATED CARTONBOARDS AS MAIN CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL WITH ABACA-WATER HYACINTH FOR SOUND ABSORPTION

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ABSTRACT

The Philippines, being within the "Pacific Ring of Fire", experiences an average of twenty (20) typhoons every year. In November 2013, Super Typhoons Haiyan (local name: Yolanda) and in December 2021, Super Typhoon Rai (local name: Odette) wreaked massive destruction. The UN OCHA Philippines Typhoon Rai Humanitarian Needs and Priorities Plan published in May 2022 stated that 2.1 million houses were damaged; 425,000 homes were destroyed, and 1,702,428 were damaged. Targeted number of people from the most vulnerable sectors for the Emergency Shelter Program (USD 30M) is 570,000. Most disaster victims and survivors sought refuge in evacuation centres, putting their health and safety at risk during a pandemic where social distance must be maintained.

KEYWORDS

Disaster Risk Reduction Management; Emergency Shelters; Bamboo-Corrugated Carton boards; Alternative Construction Materials; Abaca-Water Hyacinth; Sound Absorption; Inclusive and Sustainable Community Development and Recovery; UN SDGs

INTRODUCTION

This paper aims to provide technovative designs for flat-pack emergency shelters using corrugated carton boards and bamboo as main construction materials—all locally sourced to provide an affordable, safe, durable and climate-smart option for temporary housing. This study will also apply the “Hibla: Acoustic Fiber” (research previously presented in the Society for Science and Acoustical Society of America) which utilizes bamboo, abaca and water hyacinth to be integrated into wall panels for sound absorption, providing privacy to users. Multiple modular structures can fit into a container van. These modules can be fabricated without the need for extensive training and can be assembled on-site within hours (mainly with the use of prefabricated hinges incorporated in bamboo framing). As DRRM advocates and built environment professionals, the authors’ collective multisectoral experiences (locally and globally) in inclusive and sustainable community development rehabilitation and recovery are vital in these life-saving endeavors.

This project is in line with the Philippines Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) which was submitted to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) on 15 April 2021. As stated in the said NDC “The Philippines commits to a projected GHG emissions reduction and avoidance of 75%, of which 2.71% is unconditional and 72.29% is conditional, representing the country’s ambition for GHG mitigation for the period 2020 to 2030 for the sectors of agriculture, wastes,

industry, transport, and energy. This commitment is referenced against a projected business-as-usual cumulative economy-wide emission of 3,340.3 MtCO_{2e} for the same period.

CARDBOARD AS BUILDING MATERIAL

Emergency shelters, according to UNHCR criteria, should be composed of locally available and sustainable materials, as well as construction methods that would ordinarily be employed by the residents of the affected area for simpler assembly. The most basic construction methods and materials are always preferred.

Using cardboard as the primary wall material meets two of the most important criteria for emergency shelter building materials: cost and sustainability. When it comes to experimenting with concepts for deployable shelters, using low-cost building materials like cardboard provides a broader margin of error. Cardboard is also almost universally available and may be recycled once the module has served its purpose. Among the notable studies are the following: (a) “Efficiency of Corrugated Cardboard as Building Material” (Morad, Faggal and El Matwally, 2012); (b) “Temporary Houses from Emergency to Sustainability” (Afify, Farhat and Alhabbal, 2016); and (c) “Sustainability of Corrugated Cardboard Houses as Temporary Emergency Shelters” (Konishi and Tamura. 2002). Factors considered include production, constructability, structural safety, liveability, changes with the passage of time of temperature and humidity, use, maintenance, disassembly, demolition, withdrawal, reuse, recycle, scrapping, storage, and transport.

BAMBOO AS FRAMING MATERIAL

Proponents investigated various structural materials to see which one would be best for the emergency shelter.

Table 1. Table outlining the primary criteria for framing material selection, as well as all feasible material selections for the project.

Criteria	Steel Framing	Wood Framing	Bamboo Framing
Lightweight (Can the whole framing system of the module be carried by 3-4 persons for transportation?)	7,850 kg/m ³	1,500 kg/m ³	800 kg/m ³
Foldability (Can the frame be folded into two for easier transportation?)	Needs further studies but might be possible with light gauge steel	Yes, by using different kinds of hinges commercially available	Yes, by using different kinds of hinges commercially available
Easy Connections (Can the framing be connected by joineries without the need for welding or glue, and without the need for technical people to be on site?)	Welding must be done to connect steel frames	Yes	Yes

Bamboo framing is the most suitable material for the framing based on the requirements stated above because it is the lightest of the options available and can be connected by joineries without the need for technical people to assemble on site.

FABRICATION & ASSEMBLY PROCESS

This section of the paper illustrates the fabrication process of each module and the assembly instructions on site.

Typology

Flat pack deployable solutions offer substantial flexibility in terms of transportation and assembly, according to various architectural typologies created by previous studies on emergency shelters. With flat pack solutions, more modules can be delivered in one go since it can be stacked together.

Figure 1. Inclusion of each package consisting of 2 wall panels, 2 foldable panels, 2 engineered bamboo panels for floor and ceiling, and anchor bolts to be used on-site for assembly

Fabrication of Each Parts of the Module

Each wall panel is made up of 4" diameter treated bamboo framing and a corrugated cardboard and insulation wall. For easy assembly on-site, bamboo framings are provided with notches where walls will be fitted and fixed with anchor bolt holes at every 1.00m spacing.

Figure 2. Isometric view showing parts of the module: (1) Corrugated cardboard wall panels; (2) 4" dia. Bamboo framing; (3) Engineered bamboo flooring; (4) 2 x 4 Wood framing for flooring

Vertical bamboo frames are to be inserted in slots in the horizontal bamboo frame at the bottom of the wall panel. After placing the wall panels into the notches, L-shaped metal brackets are screwed in place on both sides to hold the corners. The same metal brackets connection are used to install and secure the horizontal bamboo frame at the top.

Each wall panel is made up of 16mm thick soundproofing composed of compacted water hyacinth fibres, sandwiched between two double flute, 7mm thick corrugated panels. These layers are all glued and pressed together during the fabrication process.

The identical procedure will be followed for the foldable wall panels, with the exception that fabricated U-shaped metal straps will be put every 1.0m at the center of the frames to allow the panel to have 180° hinges.

Figure 3. The typical wall composition of the prototype

Figure 4. Illustration showing the typical framing-to-framing connection for wall panels

Figure 5. Illustration showing the typical framing connections for foldable panels.

Figure 6. Illustration showing the suggested sequence of erecting/assembly of prototype on

Assembly on Site

On-site installation of 2.0m x 4.0m engineered bamboo planks with wood framework. Anchor bolt holes are also included in the wood framing where the (2) 2.0m x 4.0m wall panels will be mounted first. Before installing the remaining 2.0m x 4.0m engineered bamboo planks with wood framework for the ceiling, one of the 4.0m x 4.0m foldable panels must be secured in place. Finally, the last 4.0m x 4.0m foldable panel will be installed, completing one module's assembly. The proponents anticipate that the installation will take no more than 2 hours each and every module.

Figure 7. Proposed perspective of the emergency shelters after assembly on site

TRANSPORTABILITY

Each module will be packed into 2.20m x 4.50m x 1.00m high packages which can be transported through 20ft or 40ft container vans. Modules can also be transported through other modes of transportation (by sea or by air).

Figure 8. Illustration of how panels will fit into the prototype's intended packaging

Figure 9. Illustration showing the approximate dimension of the package for one module

Figure 10. Stacking of the modules inside a 40ft container van to transport.

RELEVANT ISO STANDARDS and PHILIPPINE NATIONAL STANDARDS

Table 2 shows the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards and Philippine National Standards which are relevant to the primary criteria for framing material selection and feasible material selections for the project.

Table 2. Philippine adoption of ISO standards.

ISO Standards	Philippine National Standard (PNS) Designation
ISO 21625:2020 Vocabulary related to bamboo and bamboo products	PNS ISO 21625:2021 (ISO published 2020)
ISO 21629-1:2021 Bamboo floorings — Part 1: Indoor use	PNS ISO 21629-1:2021 (ISO published 2021)
ISO 19624:2018 Bamboo structures — Grading of bamboo culms — Basic principles and procedures	PNS ISO 19624:2020 (ISO published 2018)
ISO 22156:2021 Bamboo structures — Bamboo culms — Structural design	PNS ISO 22156:2021 (ISO published 2021)
ISO 22157:2019 Bamboo structures — Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms — Test methods	PNS ISO 22157:2020 (ISO published 2019)

Bamboo-Abaca-Water Hyacinth HIBLA Acoustic Fiber Panels for Sound Absorption

For the project's sound absorption component (abaca, bamboo, and water hyacinth panels), herein authors-proponents will collaborate with the young multi-awarded research team of Hibla: Acoustic Fiber from Angeles City Science High School (Neil David Cayanan, Shaira Gozun, and E’van Relle Tongol with their mentor Lolita Bautista).

Among the national and international awards garnered by HIBLA are the following: Best Team Research Physical Science – 2019 Department of Education National Science and Technology Fair Philippines, the ISEF 2019 Acoustical Society of America - Honorable Mention, and the 2018 Young Innovators Program of the Department of Science and Technology Philippine Council for Industry, Energy and Emerging Technologies Research and Development (DOST-PCIEERD).

Below are the highlights of Hibla: Acoustic Fiber. The local testing was done by the University of the Philippines Electrical and Electronics Engineering Institute (UP-EEEI), the Metals Industry Research and Development Center (MIRDC), the Advanced Devices and Materials Testing Laboratory (ADMATEL), and the Industrial Technology Development Institute (ITDI). The Riverbank Acoustical Laboratories executed the standardized testing for impedance and absorption of acoustical materials in Illinois, USA (Cayanan, Gozun, Tongol and Bautista, L.G.,2019)

The study utilized Abacá (*Musa textilis*), Bamboo (*Bambusa merrilliana*), and Water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) that possess properties for sound absorption. The fibers were extracted, pretreated, blended with polyester (carrier fiber) in the proportion of 50:50 (biomass fiber – polyester), carded, and needle-punched. Figure 11 summarizes the methodology done in creating the sound absorption materials.

Figure 12 indicates the Normal Incidence Sound Absorption Coefficient of the *Hibla* samples and Fiberglass (positive control) from standardized testing for impedance and absorption of acoustical materials using a tube, two microphones, and a digital frequency analysis system (ASTM E1050–12).

Figure 11. Flowchart of Making the Sound Absorption Materials

Figure 12. Normal Incidence Absorption Coefficient of the samples

The utilized *Hibla* samples have the average mass and thickness of 2 g and 4.47 mm (100 mm diameter) & <1 g and 5.73 mm (29 mm diameter) for the Abacá – Polyester, 1.67 g and 9.07 mm (100 mm diameter) & <1 g and 8.17 mm (29 mm diameter) for the Bamboo – Polyester, and 2.67 g and 9.67 mm (100 mm diameter) & <1 g and 10.13 mm (29 mm diameter) for the Water hyacinth – Polyester. Conversely, the average mass and thickness of the Fiberglass were 9.33 g and 24.83 mm (100 mm diameter) & <1 g and 24.50 mm (29 mm diameter).

The sound absorption coefficient values were 0.14, 0.21, and 0.28 at 1600 Hz and 0.59, 0.58, and 0.82 at 6300 Hz, respectively for the 4.47 mm (100 mm diameter) and 5.73 mm (29 mm diameter) of Abacá – Polyester, the 9.07 mm (100 mm diameter) and 8.17 mm (29 mm diameter) of Bamboo – Polyester, and the 9.67 mm (100 mm diameter) and 10.13 mm (29 mm diameter) of Water hyacinth – Polyester. On the other hand, Fiberglass recorded sound absorption coefficients of 0.67 at 1600 Hz and 0.96 at

6300 Hz. Evidently, the sound absorption values of Abacá – Polyester (0.02), Bamboo – Polyester (0.05), and Water hyacinth – Polyester (0.06) started to increase as observed in the frequency of 500 Hz seen in Figure 12.

Moreover, the sound absorption coefficients of the control variable (Fiberglass) have close sound absorption coefficients in high frequencies with the Water hyacinth – Polyester that has the values of 0.72 (Water hyacinth – Polyester) & 0.98 (Fiberglass) in 5000 Hz and 0.82 (Water hyacinth – Polyester) & 0.96 (Fiberglass) in 6300 Hz.

The thickness of a material is only relevant in the low-frequency range (<2000 Hz) and is insignificant for the high-frequency range (>2000 Hz). In line with this, it was seen that the discrepancy in the thickness of the Hibla samples to the Fiberglass directly affects the sound absorption coefficient values in low frequencies (80 Hz – 2000 Hz), which gave an effect on the sound absorption coefficients of the samples in the given range. Furthermore, increasing the thickness of the sample will be favourable in its sound absorption property, for greater thickness helps in absorbing sound waves better and reflecting less energy from the noise. This is due to thicker materials that tend to absorb low frequencies with high wavelengths of sound more effectively, contributing to its better sound absorption.

Overall, ASTM E1050-12 validated the sound absorption coefficients of the Hibla panels specifically in the high frequencies, with test results of 0.82 for Water hyacinth – Polyester, 0.59 for Bamboo – Polyester, and 0.58 for Abacá – Polyester at 6300 Hz. Moreover, the sound absorption coefficient of the control variable Fiberglass (0.96) has a close sound absorption coefficient with the Water hyacinth – Polyester (0.82) at 6300 Hz.

Other parameters relative to being a non-woven fabric material were also tested, proving the panels' efficacy. These include its fire-resistant property (UL 94 / ASTM D618), which implies the panels' ability to prevent the spread of fire; tensile strength (ASTM D2343), stating the panels' resistance to breaking under tension; decomposition rate (Perkin Elmer STA 6000), indicating that all *Hibla* panels have a high decomposition temperature where they will start to deteriorate and release toxic trace gases; and heat-insulating capacity (Perkin Elmer STA 6000), pertaining to the ability of the panel to absorb heat energy before it heats up.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The imperative for climate-smart, resilient, affordable, and soundproof emergency shelters using local indigenous materials such as bamboo corrugated carton boards, abaca, and water hyacinth are aligned with the UN SDGs, Philippine Sustainable Finance Roadmap (2021), the Philippine Bamboo Industry Roadmap (2016), the Philippine Abaca Industry Roadmap (2018), the Philippines' Nationally Determined Contribution and the UN SDGs. The multisectoral collaboration among stakeholders in this project further supports the NDCs, to wit:

“Developed through a whole-of-government-and-society approach, the Philippines' NDC upholds the importance of meaningful participation of women, children, youth, persons with diverse sexual orientation and gender identity, differently abled, indigenous peoples, elderly, local communities, civil society, faith-based organizations, and the private sector, and recognizes the indispensable value of inclusion and collaborative participation of local governments in implementing climate actions. It shall enable a market signal to support local and foreign direct green investments. The NDC recognizes the private sector as the country's main engine of economic growth and transformation and promotes its full engagement in climate change adaptation and mitigation.”

Everything we do during and after this crisis must be with a strong focus on building more equal, inclusive and sustainable economies and societies that are more resilient in the face of pandemics, climate change and the many other global challenges we face." – United Nations Secretary-General, Antonio Guterres

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST - The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.